

Comparative Analysis of English and Uzbek Verb Phraseologisms

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Abstract: *Verb phraseologisms are considered to be essential elements of any language, demonstrating its cultural and historical individuality. In this article, a comparative analysis of English and Uzbek phraseologisms will be presented, particularly emphasizing on their structural, semantic and cultural aspects. Furthermore, this study aims to analyze the influence of linguistic and cultural contexts on phraseological expressions, through focusing on similarities and differences between English and Uzbek.*

Keywords: *English verb phraseologisms, Uzbek verb phraseologisms, comparative analysis, linguistic features, structural characteristics, semantic characteristics, metaphors, verb-noun combinations, cultural contexts, folklore influence.*

Introduction.

In the studies done by A.V. Kunin, a prominent scholar in the field of phraseology, phraseologisms were conclusively defined as “stable combinations of words with a complete or partial figurative meaning” [3, 103]. Having elaborated the works of Kunin, verb phraseologisms can be explained as “fixed or semi-fixed verbal expressions that consist of a verb as the central element and convey a figurative or idiomatic meaning that cannot be deduced from the individual meanings of their components” [3, 145].

Phraseologisms, or fixed expressions, generally not only serve to enrich a language, but also function as a key indicator of its speakers' worldview. Verb phraseologisms, in particular, are regarded as holding significant importance in the daily communication of people, expressing their complex or abstract ideas in a more concise, efficient and familiar way. By making linguistic and cultural comparisons between English and Uzbek verb phraseologisms, this article suggests the very concept of using idioms in the process of communication.

Concerning *structural features*, English and Uzbek show differences in structure patterns:

a) English Verb Phraseologisms:

✓ verbs are mainly combined with prepositions, adverbs and objects [1, 45]:

Form 1: Verb + Preposition *"Look after"* (to take care of someone or something).

Example: *"The nurse was looking after her patients."*

Form 2: Verb + Adverb *"Move on"* (to let go of the past and proceed with life).

Example: *"He struggled to move on after his wife's unexpected death"*

Form 3: Verb + Object *"Break the ice"* (to initiate conversation and reduce tension in a social situation).

Example: *"He usually uses his sense of humor to break the ice at meetings"*

✓ the employment of metaphors (word-groups comparing two unrelated things by stating that one is (or isn't) like the other) and idiomatic expressions is frequent:

- “barking up the wrong tree” (to be mistaken, to be looking for solutions in the wrong place, this expression is used as part of a sentence) [1, 45]

Example: *“In this movie, the detective always keeps barking up the wrong tree because of the tricks of the criminal.”*

✓ English verb phraseologisms tend to have fixed word order, which means that most verb phrases can only be used in a particular sequence:

- “Run into” (to meet someone unexpectedly.)

Example: *“All of a sudden, I ran into my teacher at school”*

- “Take off” (to ascend (especially in aviation) or to become successful.)

Example: *“The plane took off successfully.”*

- “Give up” (to stop doing something.)

Example: *“She is trying hard to give up smoking.”*

b) Uzbek Verb Phraseologisms:

✓ In terms of structure, in Uzbek verb-noun combinations are more commonly used:

Example: *“qora terga botmoq”* (qora – adjective, terga – noun, botmoq – verb) - to sweat heavily [2, 78].

According to Uzbek grammatical rules, it is not accepted as correct to separate word-groups in idioms to identify their word class, as the idioms do not match the actual meaning of the sentence outside the context; however, in the example above words have been classed to make the structure more understandable.

✓ Display greater flexibility in word order compared to English. There is not any particular fixed word order rules in Uzbek verb phraseologisms, as the formation of general sentence structures in the language itself is flexible.

Regarding *semantic characteristics*, both languages employ metaphoric and symbolic associations as the source from which the meanings of verb phraseologisms derive.

a) English

- Many expressions originate based on historical or cultural events, e.g., “spill the beans” (to reveal a secret), “let the cat out of the bag” (reveal a secret carelessly or by mistake) [1, 45]. Their meanings tend to be recognizable due to the global influence of English.

b) Uzbek

- Local traditions, folklore, and Islamic culture are mostly taken as a base for the origins of verb-based idioms, e.g., “og'ziga yopishmoq” (to cling to someone's words). Noticeable number of verb-phraseologisms are semantically related to nature and rural life [2, 102].

Cultural differences shape the formation and interpretation of verb phraseologisms:

➤ **English Culture** English idioms primarily reflect a history of maritime, industrial, and literary traditions. For instance, “weather the storm” refers to a seafaring background.

➤ **Uzbek Culture** Uzbek expressions are deeply rooted in agrarian and communal lifestyles. Phrases like “qo'lidan kelmoq” (to be capable) points out collectivism and resourcefulness.

Comparisons made between two languages in terms of the structural patterns and cultural context of verb phraseologisms resulted in more vivid demonstration of similar and different aspects:

1. **Similarities**

- Metaphorical imagery is a base for both languages to convey abstract ideas.
- Many expressions are originated from universal human experiences, such as life, death, and emotions.

2. **Differences**

- English phraseologisms are more broadly recognized internationally.
- Uzbek phraseologisms place more context-specific emphasis on reflecting local traditions and values.

In conclusion, the comparative analysis of English and Uzbek verb phraseologisms exhibits shared linguistic features and unique cultural identities. Understanding these expressions can make a major contribution to enhancing cross-cultural communication and appreciating linguistic diversity. Moreover, being able to comprehend the phraseologisms with understanding their root meanings in both languages can prevent possible misunderstanding or unclear conversations among speakers.

References:

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